

Cross section, Trigger and SpinDB

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1 Cross section

Figure 1: N_B particles from one bunch of blue beam collide with N_Y particles from one bunch of yellow beam with beam overlapping area A . The event cross section is σ .

In fig. 1, the probability of a certain particle from blue beam interacting with a certain particle in yellow beam to produce a certain kind of event is

$$P = \frac{\sigma}{A}. \quad (1)$$

Since there are $N_B N_Y$ possible combinations in each bunch collision, the average number of events in k_b bunch collisions is

$$N = k_b N_B N_Y \cdot \frac{\sigma}{A}. \quad (2)$$

If we define the integrated luminosity as

$$L \equiv \frac{k_b N_B N_Y}{A}, \quad (3)$$

then the event cross section is

$$\sigma = \frac{N}{L}. \quad (4)$$

This means if we want to measure a certain kind of event cross section σ , we need to know not only the number of events N , but also the integrated luminosity L . At PHENIX, we use Vernier scan technique to measure the beam overlapping area A in eq. 3. To calculate integrated luminosity in the future, notice that

$$L = \frac{N}{\sigma} \quad (5)$$

is the same for any kind of event. If we can get a “reference” event cross section σ_{ref} and its event count N_{ref} , we can calculate the integrated luminosity as

$$L = \frac{N_{ref}}{\sigma_{ref}}. \quad (6)$$

At PHENIX, we use event that triggers the BBC as such a “reference” event and measure its cross section σ_{BBC} by Vernier scan. Since σ_{BBC} is a quantity only depending on beam energy and BBC trigger efficiency, the same value can be used even for different RHIC runs if energy and BBC efficiency are the same (Of course, the colliding particles should be the same, e.g., pp, pA or AA). Then the corresponding luminosity for any event can be calculated by the corresponding BBC count N_{BBC} as

$$L = \frac{N_{BBC}}{\sigma_{BBC}}. \quad (7)$$

If we want more detailed information of the total cross section σ , we can measure its dependence on the three-momentum \mathbf{p} of the measured particle, which is called differential cross section

$$\frac{d^3\sigma}{dp^3} = \frac{d^3\sigma}{p_T dp_T d\phi dp_z}. \quad (8)$$

There is an obvious problem of the above definition, which is not invariant under boost along z-axis due to the existence of dp_z . This means eq. 8 will be different in colliding-beam and fixed-target experiments, even though all the Lorentz invariant quantities are the same. The solution is rather simple: just make the change

$$dp_z \rightarrow \frac{dp_z}{E} = dy, \quad (9)$$

where E is the energy of the measured particle and

$$y \equiv \frac{1}{2} \ln \left(\frac{E + p_z}{E - p_z} \right) \quad (10)$$

is called rapidity. It is easy to check that dy is invariant under boost along z-axis. As a result, the boost invariant differential cross section is defined as

$$\frac{d^3\sigma}{dp^3} \rightarrow E \frac{d^3\sigma}{dp^3} = \frac{d^3\sigma}{p_T dp_T d\phi dy}. \quad (11)$$

If there is azimuthal symmetry, we can integrate and average over ϕ . By substituting eq. 4,

$$E \frac{d^3\sigma}{dp^3} = \frac{1}{2\pi p_T} \cdot \frac{d^2\sigma}{dp_T dy} = \frac{1}{L} \cdot \frac{1}{2\pi p_T} \cdot \frac{\Delta N}{\Delta p_T \Delta y}, \quad (12)$$

where ΔN is the number of certain events (corrected by detector effects) in certain p_T and rapidity range. The right side of eq. 12 is what we use in measurement. If the measured particle is massless or its mass is negligible ($E \simeq |\mathbf{p}|$), we can use pseudorapidity η as an approximation of rapidity

$$y \simeq \eta \equiv \frac{1}{2} \ln \left(\frac{|\mathbf{p}| + p_z}{|\mathbf{p}| - p_z} \right) = -\ln \left[\tan \left(\frac{\theta}{2} \right) \right], \quad (13)$$

where $\theta = \angle(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{z})$ is the angle between the three-momentum \mathbf{p} of the measured particle and the positive direction of the beam axis \mathbf{z} .

2 Trigger

Trigger

Note: L1 Trigger Scaler Entries in pink indicate an approximate count due to the fact that Run Control may have crashed and the run was not ended properly.
select * from trigger where runnumber = 392548 order by bitnb

Name	Bit Mask	Scale Down	State	Raw Trigger Count	Raw Trigger Rate	Live Trigger Count	Live Trigger Rate	Scaled Trigger Count	Scaled Trigger Rate	Lifetime
BBCLL1(>0 tubes)	0x00000001	31141	Enabled	8745354585	1642011.75	8032543155	1508175.58	257933	48.43	0.92
BBCLL1(>0 tubes) novertex	0x00000002	6732	Enabled	14438675030	2710979.16	13263963189	2490417.42	1969993	369.88	0.92
ZDCLL1wide	0x00000004	6227	Enabled	1617869114	303768.14	1495142601	280725.23	240068	45.07	0.92
BBCLL1(noVtx)&(ZDCN ZDCS)	0x00000008	6396	Enabled	6580905721	1235618.80	6080495678	1141662.73	950523	178.47	0.92
BBCLL1(>0 tubes) narrowvtx	0x00000010	4070	Enabled	4215863447	791562.80	3872086615	727015.89	951139	178.58	0.92
ZDCNS	0x00000020	4411	Enabled	1096951505	205961.60	1006403083	188960.40	228106	42.83	0.92
ERT_4x4b	0x00000040	0	Enabled	591258	111.01	535155	100.48	535155	100.48	0.91
ERTLL1_4x4a&BBCLL1(noVtx)	0x00000080	0	Enabled	3672386	689.52	3369752	632.70	3369752	632.70	0.92
ERT_4x4c&BBCLL1(noVtx)	0x00000100	1	Enabled	11046812	2074.13	10206344	1916.32	5103172	958.16	0.92
SG3&MUID_1H_N S	0x00000200	95	Enabled	48406312	9088.68	44220593	8302.78	460631	86.49	0.91
ERTLL1_E&BBCLL1(narrow)	0x00000400	0	Enabled	4234416	795.05	3913981	734.88	3913981	734.88	0.92
CLOCK	0x00000800	46765	Enabled	50037096071	9394873.46	46003099421	8637457.65	983687	184.70	0.92

Figure 2: Trigger information from RHIC run 13 with runnumber = 392548.

At RHIC, the collisions generate much more data than what we are able to record. To record the data that we have more interests on, we use triggers as online selections. Fig. 2 shows the information of BBC, ZDC and ERT triggers from a particular run with runnumber = 392548. There are three kinds of trigger count: raw, live and scaled. Raw count is how many times the trigger is fired. Live count not

only requires the trigger to be fired, but also requires the data acquisition system (DAQ) is not busy and able to take data. But we don't take data as many times as live trigger count, due to limited disk space. Instead, we skip every n data after each recording. The resultant trigger count is the scaled count with scaled down = n . For example, ERT_4x4c&BBCLL1(noVtx) has scale down = 1 in fig. 2, which means if its live trigger is fired four times, it will only take the first and third data. Scale down = 0 means every time the live trigger is fired, the data will be recorded.

We use ODBC to connect to the DAQ database and SQL to query the trigger information:

```
// Use ODBC to connect to DAQ
Connection *con = DriverManager::getConnection("daq", "phnxrc", "");
Statement *stmt = con->createStatement();
ResultSet *rs = stmt->executeQuery(
    // Use SQL to query database
    "select * from trigger where runnumber = 392548 order by bitnb");
ostringstream name;
do {
    name.str("");
    rs->next();
    name << rs->getString(2);
    // Show all attributes for BBCLL1(>0 tubes) narrowvtx
    if( name.str().compare("BBCLL1(>0 tubes) narrowvtx") == 0 )
    {
        for(int ien=1; ien<=33; ien++)
            cout << "Entry " << ien << ": "
                << rs->getMetaData()->getColumnName(ien).c_str()
                << " = " << rs->getString(ien) << endl;
    }
} while( !name.str().empty() );
```

Please checkout, compile and run the code:

```
$ cd <your-source-dir>
$ cvs checkout offline/analysis/Run13ppDirectPhoton/trigger-info
$ cd offline/analysis/Run13ppDirectPhoton/trigger-info
$ ./autogen.sh
$ make
$ ./getBBCCount 392548
$ ./getBBCCount-allruns
```

getBBCCount prints trigger information for one specific run and *getBBCCount-allruns* stores trigger information for all runs in a ROOT file.

Exercise (hard): Suppose we are doing direct photon measurement with ERT_4x4c&BBCLL1(noVtx) scaled down trigger. The runlist is already contained in the code *getBBCCount-allruns.C*. After correcting detector effects, we measured number of direct photon events N_γ . We also know the BBC cross section $\sigma_{BBC} = 32.51$ mb. Please calculate the integrated luminosity L used in eq. 4 from corresponding BBC count N_{BBC} in eq. 7.

Hint: You can modify the code *getBBCCount-allruns.C* or use its output ROOT *TTree* to sum BBCLL1 (>0 tubes) novertex count. But be careful to use raw, live or scaled count. In addition, you should also take the scale down value of ERT_4x4c&BBCLL1(noVtx) into account.

3 SpinDB

The SpinDB is a special database and can also be visited by ODBC and SQL. However, there are two wrapper classes *SpinDBOutput* and *SpinDBContent* to simplify the query of SpinDB. The code *SpinDB.C* shows how to query the spin related information. You can run

```
|| $ root -l -b -q SpinDB.C\392548\
```

to print out the beam spin patterns for that run.

Exercise: Suppose we are measuring the longitudinal double-spin asymmetry of direct photon (fig. 3)

$$A_{LL} \equiv \frac{\sigma_{++} - \sigma_{+-}}{\sigma_{++} + \sigma_{+-}}, \quad (14)$$

where σ_{++} (σ_{+-}) is the cross section for the same (opposite) helicity proton collisions. As a shorthand, we write ++ (+-) for both ++ and -- (+- and -+). Eq. 14 can be rewritten in terms of direct

Figure 3: A_{LL} of direct photon.

photon yield (N) and luminosity (L) assuming that all efficiencies are helicity independent and that the beam polarizations are the same for $++$ and $+ -$. This gives

$$A_{LL} = \frac{1}{P_B P_Y} \frac{N_{++} - RN_{+-}}{N_{++} + RN_{+-}}, \quad (15)$$

where $P_{B(Y)}$ is the polarization of the RHIC blue (yellow) beam and R is the relative luminosity

$$R \equiv \frac{L_{++}}{L_{+-}}. \quad (16)$$

Main luminosity detector of this analysis is BBC. With an assumption that the proton-proton cross section for BBC trigger is the same for both $++$ and $+ -$ crossing, please calculate the relative luminosity for runnumber = 392548 by using BBC count with narrow vertex cut from SpinDB

$$R = \frac{L_{++}^{BBC}}{L_{+-}^{BBC}}. \quad (17)$$